

CLARIN in University Curricula Workshop

Utrecht, 21 - 22 April 2026

Day 2

9:00 - 13:30

Followed by lunch

Day 2 - Part 1

- **9:00 Opening and Programme Day 2**
- **9:05 - 9:35 Keynote:** *Open data, open minds: CLARIN as an educational platform in the genAI era* by [Barbara McGillivray](#)
- **9:35 - 10:35 Lightning Talks:** Emerging Practices, Platforms and Technologies in Teaching
- **10:35 - 11:00 Coffee Break**

Open data, open minds

CLARIN as an educational platform in the genAI era

Barbara McGillivray

What I'll cover

01 The landscape

02 My research as illustration

03 What students need

04 A vision for CLARIN as educational platform

The landscape our students live in

What students already do

- Use genAI to draft, summarise, and code
- Query LLMs as a first (often only) research step
- Accept fluent output as credible evidence
- Rarely interrogate training data or biases

What they don't understand

- What data these models were trained on
- How linguistic biases enter and propagate
- What interpretive assumptions are encoded
- How to evaluate or challenge AI-generated claims

Scholars or button-pushers?

We risk training a generation of button-pushers, rather than scholars who can interrogate evidence.

Tool literacy alone produces...

- Dependence on opaque systems
- No habit of inspecting sources
- Reproducibility disappears

What we should build instead...

- Critical appraisal of AI claims
- Understanding that annotation = interpretation
- Transparent, replicable research workflows

My research as illustration

What does transparent language analysis look like?

How did the word *train* change meaning during the Industrial Revolution?

With an open documented corpus

train 1820s clothing · brocade · carnations

train 1840s luggage · engine · carriages

Ask a large language model the same question

> "How did the word train change meaning during the Industrial Revolution?"

"During the Industrial Revolution, the word train shifted from describing a general trailing procession (such as a retinue, a dress skirt, or a series of horse-drawn wagons) to specifically mean a series of coupled carriages or wagons pulled by a mechanical locomotive on a railway track. This change occurred in the early 19th century, with the word becoming firmly established to describe the new steam-powered transport by the 1820s and 1830s."

No sources

Which texts? Which corpus? Unknown.

Dates vague

1830s-1840s: what evidence?

McGillivray et al. (2026) "Analysing the language of mechanisation in nineteenth-century British newspapers." *Living with Machines: Computational Histories of the Age of Industry*. University of London Press, 2025.

Open research in practice: three examples from my work

COALA

- Tracks Latin word meanings over 2000+ years
- Manual + automated corpus annotation at scale
- Every claim traceable to a text, sense inventory, and annotation decision
- All data, code, and workflows open-access

FAIR research

Journal of Open Humanities Data

- Peer-reviewed data papers: documented, citable datasets
- Makes the hidden labour of DH research visible and credible
- Datasets in open repositories
- FAIR data is what LLM training corpora are not!
- Language data reuse!

open data

SSH Open Marketplace

- Curated discovery platform: tools, workflows, training materials, datasets
- Contextualisation, curation, community
- Supported by CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA ERICs
- Directly usable in teaching

FAIR discovery ecosystem

The implication for CLARIN

Without open data and replicable workflows, claims about language risk becoming opaque, exactly the problem with large language models.

CLARIN is uniquely positioned to be the infrastructure that makes this possible at scale.

The SSH Open Marketplace: infrastructure in practice

Contextualisation

Resources are not listed in isolation, tools are linked to datasets, workflows, training and publications.

Curation

Content is curated and kept current by a community of moderators and contributors.

Community

Built and maintained collaboratively by the three ERICs and their communities. Anyone can contribute.

The screenshot displays the SSH Open Marketplace interface. At the top left is the logo for SSH Open Marketplace. A navigation bar includes links for 'Publications', 'Datasets', 'Workflows', 'Browse', 'Contribute', and 'About'. A search bar is present with a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, the page shows 'Search results' for 'ArkeoGIS'. A 'Refine your search' section includes 'Clear filters' and a dropdown menu set to 'Sort by Last modification'. A 'CATEGORIES' sidebar on the left lists: Tools & services (2366), Training materials (674), Publications (558), Datasets (1750), and Workflows (68). A 'SOURCES' sidebar on the right lists various resource families and their counts, such as CLARIN Resource Families (1558) and TAPoR (1158). The main content area features a card for 'ArkeoGIS' with a description: 'Activities Spatial Analysis Mapping Disseminating Aggregating Finding' and keywords: 'csv Consortium-HN DARIAH Resource'.

Category	Count
Tools & services	2366
Training materials	674
Publications	558
Datasets	1750
Workflows	68

Source	Count
CLARIN Resource Families	1558
TAPoR	1158
dblp: DH Publications	371
SSK Zotero Resources	333
Humanities Data	299
DARIAH-CAMPUS	227
The Programming Historian	167
CESSDA	102
Dariah.lab Poland	94
EOSC Catalogue	65
Language Resource Switchboard	47
Conversion Hub	37
Standardization Survival Kit	25
SSHopencloud Service Catalogue	18
DARIAH contribution tool	5

How CLARIN and the SSH Open Marketplace connect

What students in the genAI era need

Five things students need and CLARIN can provide

- 01 Digital text literacy**
Understanding what a corpus is, what tokenisation does, ...
- 02 Annotation as interpretation**
Students who annotate data learn that AI outputs are also interpretations, not ground truth.
- 03 Real corpora**
Authentic corpora teach linguistic intuition and cultural variation that LLM-generated text cannot replicate.
- 04 Transparent, reproducible workflows**
The full open-research cycle modelled by CLARIN infrastructure.
- 05 AI evaluation skills**
Students who understand corpora and annotation can interrogate LLM outputs

What 2019 identified, and what has changed

Where the work continues

- Teaching materials more visible but more are needed, especially discipline-specific ones
- Integration still largely depends on lecturer initiative
- Awareness beyond the consortium community remains limited
- Documentation could go further for new users

What has changed

- Students now arrive already using genAI
- Commercial AI platforms are omnipresent
- Open science requirements from funders are now structural
- The SSH Open Marketplace provides discoverable, documented workflows ready to use in teaching
- The case for open data has never been easier to make

The curriculum we need (which AI makes more urgent now)

Stable core

- Research infrastructure & metadata literacy
- Legal issues, FAIR and CARE principles
- Research data management and open science
- Standards for language resources

Flexible toolbox

- Problem-driven, not tool-driven
- Authentic datasets from CLARIN repositories
- Workflow: discovery → processing → analysis → deposit
- Discipline-specific, adaptable building blocks

Student agency

- Students deposit small corpora into CLARIN
- Publish reproducible analyses with persistent IDs
- Participate in open science culture
- Data and tools as scholarly contributions

A vision for CLARIN as educational platform

Open data, open scholarship, open minds

We should counter opaque AI with even more transparency!

Open data is a scholarly value

Transparency, reproducibility, and FAIR + CARE principles are the foundation of credible humanities research.

CLARIN is uniquely positioned

No commercial platform offers documented, community-curated, discipline-sensitive resources at scale.

Education is where this matters most urgently!

If we want AI-critical scholars, we must build AI-critical curricula now before tool-only habits become the default across a generation.

Open data as a pedagogical principle

For years, the argument for open data required effort to make outside this community. Generative AI has made it for us.

Thank you!

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Lightning Talks: Emerging Practices, Platforms and Technologies in Teaching

9:35 - 10:35

1. *Teaching Prompt Engineering for Humanists* by Federico Boschetti
2. *Integrating LLMs in corpora-related courses: annotation and fine-tuning* by Florian Kunneman
3. *Corpora and AI in linguistic tasks: casing idiomaticity* by Petya Osenova
4. *Introducing LLMs in Linguistics Teaching: A User-Centred Lexicographic Approach* by Ana Salgado
5. *Navigating the Legal Minefield: GDPR, Licensing & Ethics for Language Data* by Henk van den Heuvel

Teaching Prompt Engineering for Humanists

Federico Boschetti

CNR-ILC & CLARIN-IT

LLMs as Epistemological Disruptors

Shifting from technical skill mastery to domain competence

BEFORE LLMs

Humanists depended on programmers or programming skills to bridge code and text

The bottleneck was technical: regex, XSLT, Python, APIs

Domain knowledge alone did not grant computational agency

WITH LLMs

Natural language becomes an executable interface to tools and corpora

The bottleneck shifts: no longer code, but precise disciplinary articulation

Domain competence is now what makes the difference

→ **The disruption is epistemological, not merely instrumental**

Beyond trial-and-error

Frameworks for structured requests

ROLE

Who the model is speaking as (e.g. Latin philologist, annotator).

CONTEXT

Corpus, period, register, prior decisions, shared vocabulary

TASK

The actual operation, stated as a verb with a clear object

CONSTRAINTS

What must be preserved, excluded, or held fixed

FALLBACK

What to do when the task is under-specified or uncertain

GUARDRAIL

Failure signals the model must raise rather than silently guess

OUTPUT SCHEMA

CoNLL-U, TEI/EpiDoc, JSON schema, table

Prompts are not magic spells; they are disciplined specifications

The competence paradox

*You need experience to gain competence,
but competence to gain experience*

The trap — students without prior NLP exposure cannot evaluate whether an LLM answer is correct, so every experiment risks reinforcing plausible-sounding mistakes

The way out — scaffolded tasks where domain feedback loops (small corpora, gold standards, peer critique) make the paradox gradually productive rather than paralysing

Domain adaptation as epistemic practice

Students and LLMs mutually teach and learn: representation, operations, reasoning

REPRESENTATION

1

What counts as a unit of analysis?
Token, lemma, verse, segment,
witness. The student teaches the
model which ontology the discipline
recognises

OPERATIONS

2

Which transformations are legitimate?
Tokenisation, lemmatisation,
alignment, collation, normalisation —
each carries philological commitments

REASONING

3

Which inferences are licensed? Variant
plausibility, authorial attribution,
dating by usage — these require
justification, not probability alone

Use case: from text to linguistic analysis

From an XML-TEI document to linguistic analysis in CoNLL-U

Student role — choose the passage, justify tokenisation choices, compare two UDPipe models, document divergences philologically

Failure modes in domain-situated dialogue

- **HALLUCINATED AUTHORITY** The model cites editions, sigla, or stemmata that do not exist, in a register that mimics philological prose
- **SILENT NORMALISATION** Diacritics, abbreviations, or ligatures are tacitly modernised; the output looks clean because information was discarded
- **ANACHRONISTIC LEMMAS** Modern dictionary forms are imposed on ancient or medieval tokens, flattening diachronic variation
- **FORMAT DRIFT** CoNLL-U columns are reordered, misaligned, or invented; TEI elements close in the wrong order
- **AGREEABLE OVERRIDE** On pushback, the model reverses a correct analysis to please the user, rather than defending it with evidence

Validation as method: from lo-fi to hi-fi prompting

From lo-fi exploration to hi-fi, verifiable prompting

1

LO-FI

Free-form ask. No schema.
Assess whether the task is tractable at all

2

SCAFFOLDED

Add role, context, format.
Constrain the answer to a checkable shape

3

ANCHORED

Inject a gold snippet, a glossary,
or canonical examples as reference

4

HI-FI

Benchmark against a curated corpus; report precision, recall, disagreement

Each tier raises the cost of error detection — and the evidential value of success

Student in the loop, CLARIN in the prompt

The student is the epistemic agent

— not a passive consumer of LLM outputs, but the owner of the philological question

CLARIN in the prompt

— ParlaMint, Universal Dependencies, LINDAT services, and K-Centres supply the validation anchors that turn dialogue into evidence

Use case: validating domain-specific prompts

Against CLARIN benchmarks: ParlaMint as validation framework for parallel historical-literary editions

Why ParlaMint?

- Multilingual, parallel, TEI-native
- Consistent linguistic annotation across languages
- Stable, versioned, citable releases
- A plausible structural analogue for parallel critical editions: versions, witnesses, aligned segments

Validation workflow

- 1 Select a ParlaMint segment as a controlled baseline
- 2 Remove linguistic annotation while preserving the surface text
- 3 Apply the domain-specific prompt to the baseline segment
- 4 Compare output to baseline: measure agreement, drift, and hallucination
- 5 Deploy the prompt on the target corpus with domain adaptation checks

→ The prompt earns its status as method only when it survives a benchmark

The role of K-Centres

CLARIN Knowledge Centres as didactic infrastructure for prompt engineering

C

CURATE

Maintain domain-specific resources, gold standards, and disciplinary glossaries that prompts can reliably cite

C

CERTIFY

Offer trusted benchmarks against which LLM outputs can be measured — turning anecdote into evaluation

C

CONNECT

Link humanists, computational linguists, and infrastructure providers around shared, documented workflows

C

CASCADE

Propagate validated prompts, annotation schemes, and teaching materials across institutions and languages

→ **Prompt engineering for humanists is not an individual craft but a networked practice**

Integrating LLMs in Corpora-Related Courses: Annotation and Fine-Tuning

Florian Kunneman
University of Utrecht

Case in point

LLMs offer powerful means to analyze corpora

→ Should have a position in practicums focused on corpus analysis

But: heavy computational costs and infrastructure demands

Current practice: using 'Big Tech' applications and infrastructure

Case 1: Text and Media Analytics course

Course in the master 'Applied Data Science' at Utrecht University

Teaching students to computationally analyze Social Media

Practicum set-up: working in Google Colab notebooks

→ Free GPU availability

▾ IIIB: Fine-tuning vs. contextual embeddings as features

When we talked about the benefit of contextual embeddings, we saw an example of fine-tuning a DistilBERT model with an added layer specifically for the binary classification task. During this process, the whole model was trained (all weights were adjusted, including the newly initialized ones). Could we just use embeddings produced by the encoder model as features of our favourite classification model? We certainly could. Would it work well? Let's see.

What should we use as an embedding of the whole text, given that DistilBERT produces embeddings for each token? There are different approaches -- we could average embeddings of all tokens and use that as a sequence embedding. Alternatively -- and more frequently -- the embedding of the special token [CLS] is used for this purpose. BERT tokenizers wrap sequences into special tokens, with [CLS] token in the beginning of the sequence. [CLS] stands for 'classification' so it's not a coincidence!


```
[ ] 1 tokenizer.decode(tokenizer.encode('This is a sentence'))
```

```
▾ '[CLS] This is a sentence [SEP]'
```

Now, let's again load the DistilBERT model (now using a different class, without an added classification layer!), and use the pre-tokenized 5k examples to run them through the model and get the embeddings that we need out of it. It will take a bit of time, hold tight!

```
[ ] 1 from transformers import AutoModel
2
3 model = AutoModel.from_pretrained("distilbert-base-cased")
```

Case 2: Corpora and tools course

Course in the Bachelor 'Nederlands' at Utrecht University

Teaching students to conduct corpus studies, know how to use several tools for data collection and corpus analysis

One of the practicums: data annotation using a large language model

→ LLM web application of choice

Figure 1: Example of a systematic coding procedure.

*from: Törnberg, P. (2024). Best practices for text annotation with large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.05129*.

The following provides an example of a well-structured prompt:

Take-aways

Dependent on Big Tech to conduct assignments with LLMs

Ideal situation: applications and infrastructure hosted by trusted institution

For now: make sure that students are aware of the risks and considerations (e.g.: privacy, environment), and use LLMs in a sound way (proper data science pipeline, proper prompting)

Corpora and AI in Linguistic Tasks: Casing Idiomaticity

Petya Osenova

Sofia University and IICT-BAS

Sources Used

- **CLASSLA-express 2.0 workshop at eLex conference, 17.11.2025:** *Corpora vs. LLMs: a hands-on workshop on using CLASSLA and AI tools for phraseology and lexicography in South Slavic languages* (Organizers: Slobodan Beliga, Ivana Filipović Petrović, Apolonija Gantar, Taja Kuzman, Nikola Ljubešić, Petya Osenova, Jelena Parizoska)
- **Ljubešić et al. 2024:** Nikola Ljubešić, Taja Kuzman, Ivana Filipović Petrović, Jelena Parizoska, Petya Osenova. *CLASSLA-Express: a Train of CLARIN.SI Workshops on Language Resources and Tools with Easily Expanding Route*. In: Vandeghinste, V., & Kontino, T. (2024). *CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings 2024*, pp. 31-35. Also at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.01386>

Background (1)

- **Corpus data** have been used successfully in linguistic tasks for a long time now, providing insights into the actual language use
- During the years **corpus search tools** have become increasingly sophisticated, enabling greater automation in linguistic work by generating:
 - high-quality dictionary examples, identifying typical collocations, extracting lemma lists, statistical information of lemma and phraseology usage, and much more.
- A major step forward was the release of the CLASSLA web corpora for South Slavic languages in 2024 (Ljubešić and Kuzman, 2024) -> **the most used corpus in Bulgaria**

Background (2)

- **ChatGPT** started to be used for various linguistic tasks, especially with the help of prompt engineering to optimise results.
- In addition to benefiting from large corpora, AI tools have also been used in studies on South Slavic languages (Beliga and Filipović Petrović 2024; Gantar 2024; Gapsa et al. 2024; Kosem et al. 2024).

The Goals

- To test the capabilities of corpora and AI in performing various tasks relevant to linguists/lexicographers/philology students/ language users.
- With phraseology in focus, the aim is to contribute to two potentially challenging topics:
 - examining how language technologies perform on low and middle-resource languages such as South Slavic languages, and
 - exploring how far they have advanced in handling the ever-challenging idiomaticity, also with respect to teaching students in philology

The Tools

The tools used:

- for accessing **CLASSLA corpora** - the *NoSketch Engine* concordance
- AI-driven interfaces such as *ChatGPT 3.5* or *Gemini*

Large Corpora and AI

- **Link** <https://www.clarin.si/ske/#open>

- **Bulgarian**

CLASSLA-web.bg 2.0 (Bulgarian Web)

5,826,869,960 words

Extraction of Linguistic Information

CQL phrases NoSketch Engine

веднъж X, винаги X [*once X, always X*]

[lemma="

веднъж"]1:[tag="N.*"][] {0,1} [lemma="

винаги"]2:[] & 1.lemma=2.lemma

ChatGPT Prompt

- Here are a few sentences in Bulgarian that contain a specific phraseological construction that expresses the idea that a certain trait, behaviour, or identity, once present, is considered permanent and unchangeable:
 - Все пак нали си бегач на дълги разстояния! **Веднъж бегач, винаги бегач** [Once runner, always runner], просто ти се разшири стадионът.
 - Митове за хранителните разстройства. **Веднъж анорексик – винаги анорексик** [Once anorexic, always anorexic]. Подобно на алкохолизма, хранителните разстройства не са лечими.
 - Based on these examples:
 - Identify the construction or pattern that appears in the examples.
 - Generate *20 new examples* that follow the same structure and convey the same meaning.

Evaluation: corpus search

- Did the query successfully capture the formal pattern of the construction, or did it return noise?
- According to the number of hits and a quick look at the examples, is it a common expression in Bulgarian?
- Is the construction highly productive, showing many different realizations in the open slots, or do one or two lexical realizations dominate?
- In what kinds of texts do the constructions appear?

Evaluation: AI generated results

- Do all generated constructions follow the correct grammatical pattern?
- Do the constructions convey the same idea (that once a certain trait, behaviour, or identity is established, it is considered permanent)?
- Did the model produce surprising or humorous constructions? Were they plausible?
- Does the model add comments or explanations that were not explicitly requested (e.g. semantic interpretation, notes on typicality or frequency)?

Corpus vs. AI

- Extract the 20 most frequent examples of the construction from the corpus and compare the list with the 20 constructions generated by the AI:
 - To what extent is there overlap between corpus and AI examples?
 - Are there differences in word class? For example, are there realizations with adjectives or other word types?
 - What are the major differences in tone, register, or topic? Is there a presence of non-standard, colloquial, or coarse examples?
 - What is the ratio of positively vs. negatively toned examples?
 - Which results seem more authentic or realistic, something real speakers would say?
 - Any clear strengths or weaknesses of either approach: what does each method do better or worse?

Distinguishing literal and figurative uses

- Search for phraseological unit *падам/падна на колене* [fall to my knees] with the Filter function in NoSketch -> *падам / падна* [to fall]
- Then filter with the phrase: *на колене* [on knees]

Using the corpus

- In the concordances, find 2 examples of the actual figurative use of the phraseological unit *падам/падна на колене* [to fall on one's knees] and 2 examples of its literal use. Copy them into your working document for later.
- Next, click the *Get a random sample* icon and get 100 concordance lines.
- Manually annotate the first 20 sentences as figurative or literal using the *Concordance annotation* mode.

(This serves as a reference for evaluating the model's accuracy.)

- Then download the full set of 100 lines via the *Download* icon and save it to your computer as an XLSX file.

Using AI: prompt (1)

- Analyze the provided list of Bulgarian sentences containing the phraseological unit *падам/падна на колене* (to fall on one's knees).
- Your task is to determine whether the phraseological unit is used figuratively (idiomatically) or literally (non-idiomatically) in each sentence.
- You are looking for:
 - Literal uses, where *падам/падна на колене* describes a physical action: an actual act of falling or kneeling.
 - Figurative (idiomatic) uses, where the phrase expresses submission, defeat, collapse, admiration, or emotional surrender.
 - Examples of figurative (idiomatic) use: EXAMPLES
 - Examples of literal use: EXAMPLES

Using AI: prompt (2)

Input Format:

You will receive 100 sentences (from a corpus), each containing the phraseological unit *падам/падна на колене*.

Output Format (table with 3 columns):

Sentence – full original sentence

Label – Figurative or Literal

Short comment – one short phrase (e.g. economic collapse, admiration, prayer, emotional despair) explaining the type of meaning.

Evaluation

- How much overlap is there between your manual annotation (first 20 examples) and the AI output?
- If you had borderline cases in your manual annotation, what do you think of the AI decisions for these sentences?
- Are the AI short comments useful, for example, for linguistic purposes?
- What kinds of errors does the AI make (if any), and do they appear to be random or systematic?
- What limitations did you notice in the AI classification?
- Would you change anything in the prompt or instructions to improve the results?

References

- Beliga, Slobodan and Filipović Petrović, Ivana. 2024. Large Language Models Supporting Lexicography: Conceptual Organization of Croatian Idioms. In Proceedings of the Conference on Language Technologies and Digital Humanities, edited by Spela Arhar Holdt and Tomaz Erjavec, 23-46. Ljubljana: Institute of Contemporary History.
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- Ljubešić, Nikola, and Kuzman, Taja. 2024. CLASSLA-web: Comparable Web Corpora of South Slavic Languages Enriched with Linguistic and Genre Annotation. In Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024), 3271-3282.

CLASSLA-Express Workshops

<https://www.clarin.si/info/k-centre/workshops/classla-express/>

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Introducing LLMs in Linguistics Teaching: A User-Centred Lexicographic Approach

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A User-Centred Lexicographic Approach

- Reflection on how LLMs can enter linguistics teaching through lexicographic practice
- Case study:
 - integration of the ***Dictionary of the Portuguese Language*** of the Lisbon Academy of Sciences into **Evaristo.ai** (a Portuguese chatbot developed by the NLX group made available through **PORTULAN CLARIN**)
- Starting point:
 - not the technology alone
 - but the resource and the user
- ***What happens when we move from looking words up to asking dictionaries questions?***
- ***What might that mean for CLARIN in terms of resources, teaching, and interface design?***

From lookup to dialogue

- Traditional dictionaries are built around lemma lookup
 - users search for a word and then access its entry
- This model is still useful, but it is also rigid, entry-centred, dependent on the user already knowing what to search for
- Many real consultation needs start not from a lemma, but from a problem or a question

- A user may want to ask:
 - What is the difference between these two words?
 - How can I say this more formally?
 - How is this word pronounced?
 - What can I use instead of this word?

- LLMs make it possible to rethink dictionary consultation as:
- more dialogic, more flexible, more responsive to real consultation needs

Why lexicography matters in teaching

- Lexicography offers a productive entry point for introducing LLMs in teaching
- Dictionary use is already familiar in linguistics education
- But it also brings together many types of linguistic knowledge:
 - meaning, grammar, pronunciation
 - usage, register, variation
 - etymology, semantic relations
- The dictionary can therefore become:
 - not only a reference tool
 - but also a pedagogical interface
- From a CLARIN perspective:
 - structured language resources can support
 - consultation
 - teaching
 - critical engagement with AI

Project context: DLP-ACL + Evaristo.ai

- Ongoing integration of the Dictionary of the Portuguese Language into Evaristo.ai
- The issue is not simply placing a dictionary inside a chatbot
- It also involves thinking about:
 - what kinds of questions the system should support
 - how lexical information should be structured for interaction
 - what a dictionary-specific assistant should actually do
 - how the system can remain grounded in curated lexicographic content
- Users know they are consulting a recognised reference dictionary not an unspecified or opaque source
- This makes the project technological, linguistic, editorial, pedagogical, infrastructural

Intelligent dictionary interaction should be built on structured, curated, and trustworthy lexical resources.

 Evaristo.ai

chatbot multi-modelo e multi-heterónimo

**Ó Evaristo.ai, tens cá resposta para isto?
clicar aqui para saber...**

User evidence: questionnaire as support

- To support this reflection, a questionnaire was also carried out
- To gather empirical evidence about consultation needs; to identify user tasks
- Participants, especially students, were invited to:
 - imagine that they were talking to an intelligent dictionary
 - write at least 10 natural questions
 - indicate the kinds of answers they would like to receive
- Data collected:
 - 93 responses
 - 1,100 user questions
 - respondents included: students, teachers, researchers
- The questionnaire is not the centre of the project. It functions as:
 - a source of user evidence; map of consultation needs; input for assistant design

System design should begin from user tasks, not only from model capabilities.

And what do users want?

- Users want much more than simple definitions
- Meaning remains central, but many questions go beyond meaning retrieval
- Users also ask for:
 - synonyms and reformulations; differences between similar words; grammar and spelling; usage and context; pronunciation; etymology; semantic nuance
- So users do not simply want the dictionary to define words
- They also want it to help them: choose, compare, rephrase, understand, use words appropriately
- Users also need: reliable, credible, authoritative lexical information

A dictionary-specific assistant should not be designed only as a retrieval tool. It should support a range of lexical tasks grounded in reference lexicographic data.

What this changes in teaching

- Introducing LLMs through lexicographic practice allows them to be framed:
 - not as replacements for dictionaries
 - not as replacements for linguistic analysis
 - but as interfaces that make lexical knowledge easier to access and explore
- This creates opportunities to develop:
 - lexicographic literacy
 - better question formulation
 - awareness of different types of lexical information
 - critical evaluation of system-generated answers
- There is also a link with prompt awareness
 - asking better dictionary questions is part of learning how to interact more critically with AI-mediated language tools
- Pedagogical value:
 - lexicographic resources can help bridge
 - language knowledge
 - AI literacy and critical interaction with language technologies

Conclusion: a possible contribution to CLARIN

- LLMs should enter linguistics teaching through concrete language practices and structured language resources
- The integration of the Dictionary of the Portuguese Language into Evaristo.ai offers one example of this approach
- What matters here is not only conversational interaction
- It is also that the interaction is grounded in: a recognised reference dictionary, curated lexical knowledge, trustworthy and identifiable data
- From this case, some broader points may be relevant to CLARIN: start from user tasks, build on structured lexical resources, design for diverse dictionary interactions, connect lexicographic interfaces with teaching and AI literacy
- Users do not simply want dictionaries that define words > they want resources that help them ask better questions, make better lexical decisions, think more critically about language

Navigating the Legal Minefield: GDPR, Licensing & Ethics for Language Data

Henk van den Heuvel,
CLARIN ERIC / Radboud University

Personal data and GDPR

Personal data is any (combination of) data that can lead to the identification of an individual

GDPR The Six Legal Bases for Processing (Article 6):

- **Consent**: The individual has given clear, freely given, and specific consent.
- **Contract**: Processing is necessary for a contract with the individual or to take steps before entering into a contract.
- **Legal Obligation**: Processing is required to comply with the law (not applicable to contractual obligations).
- **Vital Interests**: Processing is necessary to protect someone's life.
- **Public Task**: Processing is necessary to perform a task in the public interest or for official functions.
- **Legitimate Interests**: Processing is necessary for your organization's legitimate interests or a third party's interests, provided they do not override the individual's fundamental rights.

Privacy by design in research

Build in privacy-enhancing measures in the design of your research.
Without a good plan, opportunities for data breaches are growing.

There are 8 guidelines for
Privacy by Design:

- Data minimization
- Data quality
- Goal setting
- Minimization of use
- Security measures
- Transparency
- Rights of data subjects
- Liability

Privacy by Design

Een korte instructieve video over richtlijnen voor het gebruik van persoonsgegevens door medewerkers van de RU (animatie: Rikkert Veltman)

[Privacy RU website, incl. video](#)

Open Data

- Open Data = (research) data that is **freely available online for (re)use and republish** for everyone provided that the data source is attributed
- Open Data means: “**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**”
- Also closed access data can be stored FAIR provided that the access terms are transparent and public
- Sharing is not giving away, to work in an open environment benefits all, especially the data sharer
 - reach as many people as possible
 - be cited more often
 - build cooperation
 - etc.

Archiving and publishing data

Distinguish Access levels

- Open / public
- Restricted
- Closed

Use a trusted repository, e.g. CLARIN Data centers

- See <https://www.clarin.eu/content/overview-clarin-centres>

Select an appropriate Data Use Agreement (DUA) / License

- See e.g. <https://www.clarin.eu/content/licenses-and-clarin-categories>
- <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

DELAD Introduction

- DELAD: <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/>
 - DELAD is an initiative to share corpora of speech of individuals with communication disorders (CSD) among researchers. We do this in a GDPR compliant way and at secure repositories in the CLARIN infrastructure.
- Part of CLARIN K-Centre for Atypical Communication Expertise (ACE; <https://ace.ruhosting.nl>)
- CLARIN Data Centre: The Language Archive (TLA) at the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics (<https://tla.mpi.nl>)
- <https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpora-disordered-speech>
- Cool materials on DELAD website:
 - <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/wordpress/guidelines-consent-storage/>
 - <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/wordpress/guidelines-annotations/>
 - <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/wordpress/dpia-role-play-with-video/>

Privacy by Design course offered by CLARIN

<https://www.clarin.eu/learning-resources-catalogue/>

Part 1: Privacy by design in research intro

Part 2: Group discussion Use Cases 1 & 2

Part 3: DPIA Roleplay Use Case 3

See also <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/wordpress/dpia-role-play-with-video/>

Day 2 - Part 2

- **10:35 - 11:00 Coffee Break**
- **11:00 - 11:15** Finding and Reusing Open Educational Resources: CLARIN Learning Hub, H2IOSC and SSH Open Marketplace
- **11:15 - 12:15 Breakout Session 2:** *Co-Designing Reusable Outputs for the Community*
- **12:15 - 13:00** Plenary reporting & Discussion
- **13:00 - 13:30** Conclusions & Next Steps: From Workshop Results to Community Action
- **13:30 - 15:00** Networking & Closing Lunch

Finding and Reusing Open Educational Resources: CLARIN Learning Hub, H2IOSC and SSH Open Marketplace

Thalassia Kontino, CLARIN ERIC

Giulia Pedonese, CNR-ILC / CLARIN-IT

11:00 - 11:15

CLARIN Learning Hub

Tutorials

This section features tutorials created by the CLARIN central hub for training workshops and other events as well as materials developed within EU-funded projects.

[Explore →](#)

Learning Resources Catalogue

The Learning Resources catalogue showcases open educational materials produced within the CLARIN community, in the context of university teaching, training, and workshop events.

[Explore →](#)

Digital Humanities Course Registry

The Digital Humanities Course Registry, set up in collaboration with our partner, DARIAH-EU, is a great place to find up-to-date university courses and summer schools in Europe and beyond.

[Explore →](#)

Guidelines and Best Practices

Trainers and educators who wish to develop learning content based on best practices in the CLARIN community and wider SSH network are invited to browse the resources on this page.

[Explore →](#)

Trainers' Network

CLARIN's community of experts and trainers deliver training activities such as workshops and webinars in many disciplines, including linguistics, digital humanities, and social sciences.

[Explore →](#)

- A central place for educational materials
- Can be used to browse for tutorials, Digital Humanities programmes, as well as guidelines and best practices for using the infrastructure in teaching

CLARIN Learning Resources Catalogue

- A **curated catalogue** of educational materials from the CLARIN community,
- Filters to narrow your research results by **topic, skill level, resource type**, and more
- Based on the RDA Minimal Metadata schema for Learning Resources

Filters:

Topic

- + [Research](#)
- + [Infrastructures](#) (14)
- + [Research Data Management](#) (8)
- + [Corpus Linguistics](#) (6)
- + [Digital Humanities](#) (5)
- + [Computational Linguistics](#) (8)

[Show more](#)

Skill level

- + [Basic](#) (22)
- + [Intermediate](#) (15)
- + [All](#) (7)
- + [Advanced](#) (6)

Target audience

- + [Researchers](#) (23)
- + [Students](#) (16)
- + [Teachers](#) (11)
- + [PhD students](#) (3)

Learning Resource Type

- + [Course](#) (15)
- + [Tutorial](#) (12)
- + [E-learning module](#) (11)
- + [Lesson](#) (4)
- + [Unit](#) (3)

[Show more](#)

National Consortium

- + [clarin-it](#) (6)
- + [clarin-si](#) (4)
- + [clarin-hl](#) (2)
- + [clarin-4](#) (2)
- + [clarin-it](#) (2)

[Show more](#)

Media Type

- + [text](#) (42)
- + [video](#) (13)
- + [others](#) (4)
- + [audio](#) (3)
- + [h5p](#) (2)

Licence

- + [CC-BY 4.0](#) (35)
- + [CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0](#) (5)
- + [CC-BY-SA 4.0](#) (4)
- + [2024 edX LLC. All rights reserved.](#) (2)
- + [CC-BY-NC 4.0](#) (2)

Home / Learning Hub / Learning Resources Catalogue

Learning Resources Catalogue

The Learning Resources catalogue showcases open educational materials produced within the CLARIN community, in the context of university teaching, training, and workshop events. The catalogue can be browsed by topic, skill level and resource types, etc. Each entry is described with consistent metadata, including educators' experience with using the CLARIN infrastructure resources for teaching and learning. All resources are released under a Creative Commons Licence. To propose a new learning resource or materials for the catalogue, please email training@clarin.eu.

Displaying 1 - 50 of 50 learning resources

 Items per page: 50 ▾

Introduction to Digital Humanities

This course offers an introduction to the field of Digital Humanities, focusing on the principles and practices involved in the processing and analysis of ...

Target Audience: [Students](#)

Licence: [CC-BY 4.0](#)

Skill Level: [Basic](#)

Keywords: [data-driven research](#), [digital content processing](#), [text processing](#), [image processing](#), [metadata](#), [word embeddings](#), [research infrastructures](#)

Collecting Language Data from Human Participants

This learning resource is focused on collecting language data from human participants and is structured into four modules , complemented by two student projects ...

Target Audience: [Teachers](#)

Licence: [CC-BY 4.0](#)

Skill Level: [Intermediate](#)

Keywords: [data collection](#), [sociolinguistics](#), [second-language acquisition](#), [morphosyntax](#), [research methods](#)

Introduction to Oral Data Management

The course addresses issues related to the management of oral linguistic data. After a general introduction to the options offered by the CLARIN [ERIC](#) ...

Target Audience: [Researchers](#)

Licence: [CC-BY 4.0](#)

Skill Level: [Advanced](#)

Keywords: [oral archives](#), [speech and oral data](#), [data management](#), [automatic transcription](#)

Overview of Topics & Resource Types

Minimal RDA Metadata Set for Learning Resources

- **Descriptive INFO:** Title, Abstract, Author(s), Language, Keyword(s), Version Date
- **Access INFO:** URL, Access Cost, Resource URL type, Licence
- **Educational INFO:** Target group, Learning resource type, Learning outcome(s), Expertise level

- + CLARIN K-Centre, National Consortia
- + More resource types

Resource Example

Introduction to Oral Data Management

The course addresses issues related to the management of oral linguistic data. After a general introduction to the options offered by the CLARIN *ERIC* infrastructure in the process of discovering, collecting and storing oral data, the course will explore the ethical and legal issues related to data collection, management and storage, and the process of automatic transcription, with additional annotation options using automatic language processing tools.

Author: Christoph Draxler, Henk van den Heuvel, Iulianna van der Lek, Francesca Frontini, Giulia Pedonese

Learning Outcomes:

Use the search, annotation and deposit services offered by CLARIN *ERIC* - Understand and apply national guidelines on personal data protection relating to the collection, management and storage of spoken language data - Evaluate machine translation techniques and the software best suited to your research project.

Prerequisites:

Knowledge of linguistic and experimental phonetic methods and the basic principles of corpus linguistics.

Target Audience: [Researchers](#)

Skill Level: [Advanced](#)

Keywords: [oral archives](#), [speech and oral data](#), [data management](#), [automatic transcription](#)

Licence: [CC-BY 4.0](#)

Publication Date: 7 May 2025

Last Modified: 7 May 2025

Topic: [Research Data Management](#)

Language:

Italian

Learning Resource Type: [Course](#)

URL To Resource:

<https://h2iosc-training-library.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/ricerca/archive/150>

Citation:

Christoph Draxler, Henk van den Heuvel, Iulianna van der Lek, Francesca Frontini, & Giulia Pedonese. (2025). Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali. H2IOSC Training Library. pm0wTlnXwKiHQV82JPOGjDM7oW7Zngj.

CLARIN-IT for H2IOSC - Introduction and context

WP8: Training, Capacity Building, Engagement

- **FAIR-Training** methodology
- Two training platforms: a Management System for **e-learning** and a **Repository** for trainers

H²IOSC
Training Environment

H²IOSC
Training Library

≡ [Indice](#)

[Chiudi](#) ✕

Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists

[Indice](#)

[Eventi](#)

▼ Course Outline

- [Welcome](#)
- Syllabus
- Introduction and Acknowledgements

▼ Linked Data Fundamentals

- [Linked Data Fundamentals](#)

▶ Language Resources, FAIR Principles and Linked Open Data

▶ Exploring the Semantic Web Stack

▶ Focus on Lexicons and Dictionaries in RDF

▶ Applied Latin

DASHBOARD

I MIEI CORSI

CERCA NEL CATALOGO

CALENDARIO

FAQ

ABOUT

Welcome

Welcome to the course "Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists"

Cover image: Futuristic digital matrix particles grid virtual reality abstract cyber space environment background by [Kittiphap](#) via [Adobe Stock](#)

Cerca nel catalogo

[Ricerca avanzata](#)

Le Applicazioni Pratiche di Weblight: Ricer...

OPERAS @ H2IOSC Café

Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Standard e...

Iluliana van der Lek, Darja Fiser, Francesca Frontini, Giulia Pedonese

Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists

Anas Fahad Khan, Giulia Pedonese, Michele Mallo, Eliso Squadrino, Francesca Frontini, Valerio Quochi

Introduzione alle Digital Humanities e all'In...

Andrea Bolioli, Paolo Monella, Emmanuel Corbé, Mariangela Giglio, Enrica Salvatori, Salvo Spina, Francesca Frontini, Alessio Scacchi, Rachele Sprugnoli...

Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali

Iluliana van der Lek, Francesca Frontini, Christoph Draxler, Henk van den Heuvel, Giulia Pedonese, Roberta Bianca Luzietti, Roberto Ottaviani

Language and Accent Discrimination - CIR...

Claudio Soria, Francesco Gallina, Rob Drummond, Alice Henderson, Sender Davchin, Ana Tankosic, Giuliana Regnoli, Silvia Calamai, Clara Molina, Alex Baratta

CLARIN-IT: Dati Linguistici, Standard e Str...

Monica Manacchini, Angelo Mario Del Grosso, Giulia Pedonese

Fare didattica con gli archivi orali

Giovanni Abate, Cesarina Vecchia, Silvia Calamai, Sergio Conazzo, Alessandro Casellato, Evira Mercatanti, Monica Manacchini, Virginia Neri, Giulia Ziletti Conti, Giad...

Current Topics in Heritage Science

Katrien Keune, Vivi Tomari, Zvi Karen, Daniel O'Flynn, Michele Botticelli, Bernhard Blumich, Piotr Targowski, Pascale Friture, Vincent Lobbas, Emilio Cano

Digital Humanities e Intelligenza Artificiale...

Marina Buzzoni, Cristina Marras, Alice Orriù, Giulia Pedonese, Francesca Frontini, Alessio Scacchi, Paolo Menella

What is the H2IOSC Training Library?

The H2IOSC Training Library is a repository designed for the deposit and storage of reusable teaching material for teachers and trainers. Through a simple and intuitive search interface, the platform allows:

- ✔ Publication of training materials
- ✔ Long term curation
- ✔ free download of teaching modules

The platform enables teachers and trainers to publish their own teaching products to see their work reused and correctly cited by colleagues who wish to adapt it. On the other hand, the platform will provide a means of discovery and reusable teaching material to facilitate and enrich the work of teachers .

What can you do on the H2IOSC Training Library?

Search for a training module ✔

Browse a rich catalogue of reusable training materials under open licenses and refine your search with facets.

Save your results ✔

Authenticate with SSO to manage your personal page with your bookmarks

Publish your training materials ✔

Submit your resource through the reviewing process and become a contributor

Learning Content Structure

Ultima modifica: admin h2iosc 22/05/2025 12:01:52 Stato della scheda: ● **Publicato**

- GERARCHIA
- Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Stand...
- Introduzione al Ciclo di Vita e alla G...
 - Cosa sono le risorse linguistiche?
 - Come Vengono Create, Gestite e...
 - Panoramica degli Standard e dei...
 - Il Ruolo delle Infrastrutture di Ri...
 - CLARIN: un Esempio di Infrastru...
 - Creare un Piano di Gestione dei ...
 - Risorse aggiuntive e fonti
 - L'impatto sociale delle risorse li...
 - Applicare i principi FAIR ai corpo...
 - Come Rendere FAIR i Dati Linguisti...
- Trovare e (ri)utilizzare le Risorse Li...
- Citare i Dati Linguistici
- Questioni legali ed etiche nella rac...
- Progetto per Studenti
- Glossario

Learning Content Structure | Media

Structure Identifier Metadata License agreement

- 1 - Learning Path
- 2 - Course
- 3 - Section
- 4 - Module
- 5 - Unit
- ✓ 6 - Learning Object

STRUCTURE

Level & record type

Parent: Introduzione al Ciclo di Vita e alla Gestione delle Risorse Linguistiche

Title: Creare un Piano di Gestione dei Dati per la Ricerca Linguistica

IDENTIFIER

Element with PID: Yes

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

Persistent identifier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911935>

Record Minimi: 0 + Aggiungi un record

METADATA

Abstract: Secondo Kung (2022), ci sono sei aspetti importanti che devono essere considerati e pensati quando si sviluppa un piano di gestione dei dati di ricerca: raccolta, analisi e gestione dei dati; requisiti legali ed etici della raccolta e dell'uso dei dati; archiviazione, backup e sicurezza dei dati; documentazione e metadati; diffusione, conservazione e

AUTHOR(S)

Record Minimi: 1 + Aggiungi un record

Annulla

...erito, è necessario inserire almeno 1 record(s)

Marketplace H²IO OSC

Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

All categories ▾

Search tools, datasets, workflows...

Search

 Semantic search

H²IO OSC Training Library

H²IO OSC Training Environment

Training

Learn how to discover, use, manage and preserve research data

Upcoming Events

Fri 20 Feb 2026
SSHOC Workshops: FAIR, CARE & Open Science Principles
The SSH Open Marketplace Editorial Board invites you to a hands-on workshops to strengthen FAIR...

Mon 23 Feb 2026
I4NG Make it Green: Insights on climate action and public perception
This workshop, hosted by the Infra4NextGen

Featured Resources

The Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG) is a comprehensive guide to Research Data Management and FAIR data principles.

 Data Management Expert Guide

The Data Archiving Guide (DAG) is designed to provide new employees at social science data archives with a general understanding of the work a

Sign in

Training

Home / Training

Home / Learning Hub / Learning Resources Catalogue

Learning Resources Catalogue

The Learning Resources catalogue showcases open educational materials produced within the CLARIN community, in the context of university teaching, training, and workshop events. The catalogue can be browsed by topic, skill level and resource types, etc. Each entry is described with consistent metadata, including educators' experience with using the CLARIN infrastructure resources for teaching and learning. All resources are released under a Creative Commons Licence. To propose a new learning resource or materials for the catalogue, please email training@clarin.eu.

Displaying 1 - 48 of 48 learning resources

Search

Items per page: 50 ▾

Interaction with H2IOSC Marketplace

The screenshot displays the H2IOSC Marketplace interface. At the top left is the H2IOSC logo, and at the top right is a search icon and a menu icon labeled 'menu'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Results'. A search bar contains the text 'Search tools, datasets, workflows...'. A 'Semantic search' button is visible. On the left side, there is a 'Refine search' section with a 'Save search' button and a 'Clear all filters (1)' button. Below this is a 'Category' section with a list of categories: Tool (24), Dataset (19), Service (15), Publication (6), Learning resource (5), Application Workflow (4), Descriptive Workflow (4), and Project (1). The 'Tool' category is selected. Below the categories is an 'Infrastructure' section, a 'Year of publication' section, and a 'Language' section. The main content area shows search results. The first result is 'STONEVERSE', a tool with a 'Free access' button, dated 30/01/2026, version 1.00.00, and 3 items. The description states: 'STONEVERSE is a platform developed in DARIAH for cultural heritage. STONEVERSE provides numerical models, in order to create scenarios of degradation...'. Below this are buttons for 'Save', 'Share', 'Cite', and 'Export'. The second result is 'Test - Arquivo.pt', also a tool with 'Free access', dated 30/01/2026, version 1.0, and 1 item. The description states: 'Arquivo.pt - the Portuguese web-archiver is a resource since 1996. Its main objective is the preservation of...'. A dropdown menu is open over the search bar, listing categories: All categories, Tool, Dataset, Publication, Project, Service, Terminology resource, Learning resource (highlighted with a red circle), Descriptive Workflow, and Application Workflow. The 'View' options are set to 'List' and 'Grid'.

- **H2IOSC Marketplace:**
unique access point for data, tools, services and training
- **Integration** of the Training Library and Training Environment contents
- **Controlled vocabularies** (SSHOC) and shared metadata for interoperability

Reusing teaching modules at Universities

Descrizione

Benvenuti nel corso "Introduzione alla gestione dei dati linguistici: Standard e Archivi Digitali"

Immagine di copertina: Circuit connect lines and dots. Network technology and Connection concept. Decentralized network nodes connections. Di [natrot](#) tramite [Adobe Stock](#)

- ine
- n and Acknowledgements
- 1 Fundamentals
- a Fundamentals
- resources, FAIR Principles Open Data
- ie Semantic Web Stack
- xicons and Dictionaries in
- ID: the Case of LILa-Linking

Welcome

Welcome to the course "Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists"

cover image: Futuristic digital matrix particles grid virtual reality abstract cyber space environment background by [Kittiphat](#) via [Adobe Stock](#)

2024 CLARIN Courses @ UniFe

Course	Level	Lesson 1	Lesson 2	Total duration	Attendance
English Language for Translation	MA	April 18 Teacher: Del Fante	April 19 Teacher: Del Fante	4 hours	25 students
English Language and Linguistics for Humanities, Arts and Archaeology	BA	May 9 Teacher: Pedonese	May 17 Teacher: Del Fante	4 hours	30 students
English Language for Tourism	BA	May 10 Teacher: Pedonese	May 14 Teacher: Del Fante	4 hours	40 students

2025 CLARIN Courses @ UniFe

1. **A module on CLARIN core services** via the Virtual Training Environment, adapted from UPSKILLS
2. **Introduction to Linked Open Data** adapted to BA and MA level courses:
 - Linked Data fundamentals
 - Language Resources, FAIR principles and Linked Open Data
 - Exploring the Linguistic Linked Open Data Cloud
 - Brief SPARQL tutorial (MA students)

Related activities

CLARIN Café on Translation Technologies

This experience revealed the community's need for more teaching tools on translation technologies.

We organised a CLARIN Café on this topic and opened it to the entire community of researchers and trainers in this field.

The **CLARIN Café on Translation Technologies & Workflows for SSH Researchers** was held on June 14, 2024

Adapting UPSKILLS Learning Modules to the University Curricula

Best Practices and Lessons Learnt from the H2IOSC Training Experience at the University of Ferrara

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3384/ecp216.04>

Giulia Pedonese, Francesca Frontini, Dario Del Fante, Eleonora Federici

37-47

PDF

Selected papers from the CLARIN Annual Conference 2024

This volume presents the highlights of the thirteenth CLARIN Annual Conference in 2024. The conference took place from 15 to 17 October 2024 in Barcelona, Spain.

Series: Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings 216

Editors: Vincent Vandeghinste and Thalassia Kontino

ISBN: 978-91-8118-188-3

ISSN: 1650-3686 (print), 1650-3740 (online)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3384/ecp216>

Published: 2025-08-25

Università
degli Studi
di Ferrara

ITA ▾

🔗 / 3rd International ELT Conference

Condividi

3rd International ELT Conference

Breakout Session 2:
***Co-Designing Reusable Outputs for the
Community***

11:15 - 12:15

Groups

1. Group A - CLARIN Toolkit for Lecturers
2. Group B - Communication Pack for University Alliances
3. Group C - Classroom-friendly infrastructure checklist
4. Group D - Reusable teaching modules

Plenary reporting & Discussion

12:15 - 13:00

Each group will present:

- **What it produced**
- **What further development would be required**
- **Who is willing to contribute to follow-up work**

10-12 min per group, incl. Q&A

Plenary Reporting

1. Group A - CLARIN Toolkit for Lecturers
2. Group B - Communication Pack for University Alliances
3. Group C - Classroom-friendly infrastructure checklist
4. Group D - Reusable teaching modules

Conclusions & Next Steps: From Workshop Results to Community Action

13:00 - 13:30

Conclusions

1. Curriculum Integration Requires Strategic Thinking

CLARIN and digital tools are too often treated as add-ons rather than being meaningfully embedded in curricula. Effective integration requires curriculum literacy, understanding what levels (supra, macro, meso, micro, nano) you can realistically influence, and acting smartly within those constraints.

2. The "Why" Must Come Before the "What"

CLARIN integration is only meaningful when it is aligned with clear learning objectives and pedagogical intent, not driven by tool availability.

3. AI Is the Elephant in the Room

Students increasingly use AI tools uncritically, skipping methodological steps and lacking skills in source criticism, quality assessment, and reproducibility. There is an urgent need to teach responsible, explainable AI use, and CLARIN offers a pedagogically sound foundation through authentic, curated, FAIR language data that LLM training corpora typically lack.

4. Data Citation and Research Data Management Are Underserved Skills

Data citation is not yet common practice, and many students, especially early-stage PhD researchers, lack research data management (RDM) skills. CLARIN can play an active role by promoting citation examples, improving metadata quality, and supporting RDM training initiatives such as the DocEnhance Data Stewardship course.

Conclusions

5. Practical, Discipline-Specific Resources Are Key to Adoption

Teachers need ready-to-use, adaptable materials, concrete examples, slides, working pipelines, and discipline-specific problem-driven scenarios, to confidently integrate CLARIN into their teaching. Fear and unfamiliarity are real barriers that targeted support can address.

6. Multiple Entry Points Are Needed

Outreach should go beyond individual lecturers to include university libraries, teaching and learning centres, and institutional administration. Success stories, road shows, tailored lectures, and ministry-level engagement are all viable channels for raising awareness and embedding CLARIN at higher curricular levels.

7. Collaboration and Community Are Essential

No single actor can drive change alone. Sustainable integration requires collaboration between research communities, teachers & trainers, RDM experts, CLARIN National Consortia, and institutions, sharing materials, reusing outputs, and also connecting to other research infrastructures, e.g SSH Marketplace, Hugging Face etc.

Conclusions

- Toolkit: More use cases that are relevant and specific to specific communities (e.g., librarians, translators etc.)
 - Ready to use presentations that are smaller for specific topics (what is CLARIN?)
 - Fewer best practices
- We need more training officers in the national consortia
- Collect list of university alliances and see which are relevant
- Turn AI into an asset
- Topics should be problem oriented and not resources oriented as it's currently
- A chatbox that you would put your research questions and see which CLARIN resource is useful
- Tutorials on evaluating resources
 - Students should learn that imperfect data and annotations are a part of research
- Share knowledge about hardware infrastructures

Possible Next Steps

- Publication outputs, e.g. research article based on a wider survey / comparative analysis per national consortia/position paper?
- Task groups? Which topics should we prioritize?
- When do we meet again? Every two years?

Levels to address

- Levels:
 - **Supra:** International, comparative
 - **Macro:** System/society/nation/state
 - **Meso:** Institution
 - **Micro:** Classroom (e.g., syllabi, assignments, assessments)
 - **Nano:** Individual/personal (e.g., student experience)

Flipping the iceberg

Hidden curriculum

- Stakeholder expectations and values ✓
- Technological developments ✓
- Disciplinary norms ✓
- Time pressure and workload realities ✓

Image by MoteOo from Pixabay

Feedback

<https://www.menti.com/alc72cvr62oa>

